

Comparative and optimization study of utilizing alginate and agar flocculants for water treatment

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Abstract. Recently, bio-based flocculants such as organic polymers have gained lots of consideration in water treatment technology owing to their superior advantages in excess of conventional synthetic inorganic polymers. A comparative study of two organic flocculants (sodium alginate and agar) for the treatment of surface water is aimed in this study. The influence of adding dry yeast (1, 2 & 3%) on the turbidity removal was studied. Adding 1% dry yeast improved the performance of both alginate and agar as a flocculating agent (percent removal of turbidity 62% and 60% after 60 min, respectively), but increasing the amount of dry yeast was not helpful. Optimal conditions for the turbidity removal process were obtained using response surface methodology. Based on the predicted linear models, the optimum parameters were 1.3 g alginate and 1.6 g agar for 59 min. Maximum turbidity removal achieved at these conditions were 62.4 and 59.7%, respectively. Thus, it is important to have further research on this natural coagulant for the future development of green technology in the water treatment process.

Introduction

The quality of water for the purpose of human consumption has been of interest since its effects on health was first discovered. Considering the increase in demand and the decrease in resources, water as essential fluid of life is a scare commodity [1]. Suspended and colloidal matters in water result in turbidity, they form a stable colloidal suspension that do not settle readily but remain in suspension [2]. Not only due to the appearance reasons but also its potential health risks turbidity is an important parameter stated in drinking water quality criteria. Primary contributors to turbidity include clay, silt, finely divided organic and inorganic matter, soluble colored organic compounds, plankton, and microscopic organisms [3,4].

For water treatment facilities to produce safe drinking water from river water, removing turbidity from the water is a challenge [5], particularly during the dry season when silt is carried into the pumping well. Coagulation and flocculation are the most economic methods for turbidity removal from water [6]. For the traditional reduction of turbidity in raw water, inorganic coagulants like alum and lime were used. The sludge obtained from such treatment poses disposal problems and tends to accumulate in the environment [7,8].

Recently, bio-based flocculants have received a lot of attention due to their superior advantages over conventional synthetic polymers or inorganic agents. Among natural polymers, polysaccharides show many benefits such as biodegradability, non-toxicity, ability to undergo different chemical modifications, and wide accessibility from renewable sources [9,10]. Several studies have tested different types of natural flocculants such as plant based coagulants [11-13], and different polysaccharides such as sago and chitin [14]. Although many studies have been conducted on the use of alginate as a flocculating agent, it is still in its infancy [15].

Alginate and agar are natural polymers with promising challenges as flocculating agents for water and wastewater treatments due to their biodegradability and non-toxicity. The present study is an attempt to compare and optimize the efficacy of using these natural polymers as a natural flocculants with a view to achieving the best results in moving towards a treatment for drinking water that meets the sustainable developing goals.

Materials and Methods

Materials. Sodium alginate powder, calcium chloride and agar powder were purchased from El-Gomhouria Pharmaceuticals and Chemicals Company, Cairo, Egypt.

Synthetic water. Synthetic water was prepared by adding garden soil to tap water and left mixing by magnetic stirrer for 1 hour. The suspension was then allowed to stand for 2 hours and after that, the supernatant was taken and served as the sample for the experiments. Table 1 shows the main features of the prepared synthetic water.

Table 1. Features of the prepared synthetic water

Parameter	Water
PH	7.14
Turbidity	88-92 NTU
Temperatur e	25-26 °C

Alginate and agar beads preparation

Alginate beads preparation. Alginate beads were prepared using sodium alginate solution (4% w/v) dripped into calcium chloride solution (4% w/v) using a syringe, then the solution of calcium chloride with drops of alginate solution is put into the fridge for 1 hour. Then the alginate beads are washed with distilled water in order to be used for the flocculation experiment. Alginate beads with dry yeast were prepared by adding 1, 2 and 3% dry yeast.

Agar beads preparation. Agar beads were prepared using 3 g of agar powder/100 ml of distilled water and left the flask with a solution in hot water bath with a temperature 100 °C for 1 hour. Then the agar solution is poured into a plate after this the solution of agar in the plate is left to cool for 10 min out the fridge and then for 30 min in the fridge. Then the plate of agar is gotten out from the fridge, cut the agar to small beads in order to be used for the flocculation experiment. Agar beads with dry yeast were prepared by adding 1, 2 and 3% dry yeast.

Flocculation procedure. For different types of prepared beads (alginate beads, alginate with yeast beads, agar beads and agar with yeast beads); different amounts (1, 2, 3 and 4g) of beads were put each weight in a beaker with 100 ml of synthetic water with initial turbidity 90 NTU and then allow mixing at high speed for 2 min then mixing at slow speed for 10 min then allowed for settling through different time periods (30, 40, 50 and 60 min), then the final turbidity was measured using turbidity meter.

Analytical methods. Final turbidity was measured using turbidity meter (Lutron TU-2016).

Experimental design and data analysis

Response surface methodology was utilized to optimize the process response (turbidity removal percent). Central composite design (face centered) with three coded levels leading to nine sets of experiments was performed to evaluate the effect of the independent process variables (grams of beads/100 ml turbid water, and settling time). Experimental process variables and levels for the design are given in Table 2. Design-Expert 10.0.1 software was used for the statistical analysis.

Table 2. Experimental range and levels of the independent process variables

Independent variable	Symbol	Range and levels		
		-1	0	+1
Grams of beads/100 ml turbid water	X_1	1	2	3
Settling Time (min)	X_2	40	50	60

Results and Discussion

Effect of alginate beads on turbidity of water. Fig. 1 shows that by increasing the amount of alginate beads in the turbid water, the turbidity decreased and by increasing the time of settling, turbidity of water decreased too. Also, Fig. 2 shows that adding 1 g of dry yeast help to improve the ability of alginate beads to remove turbidity from water but increasing the amount of dry yeast in the prepared alginate beads is not more helpful in turbidity removal as shown in Table 3.

Effect of agar beads on turbidity of water. Fig. 3 shows that by increasing the quantity of agar beads in the turbid water, the turbidity decreased slightly. But, increasing the settling time decreases the turbidity of water. So, agar is not a better choice to eliminate turbidity of water at these conditions. Fig. 4 shows that adding 1 g of dry yeast help to increase the ability of agar to eliminate turbidity from water but increasing the quantity of agar with 1g dry yeast in water is not more helpful in the turbidity removal. Also, increasing the quantity of dry yeast doesn't help to improve the ability of agar to eliminate turbidity of water (Table 3).

Fig. 1. Turbidity removal using alginate beads

Fig. 2. Turbidity removal using alginate beads with 1% dry yeast

Fig. 3. Turbidity removal using agar beads

Fig. 4. Turbidity removal using agar beads with 1% dry yeast

Table 3. Effect of dry yeast concentration on turbidity removal using 1 g beads/ 100 ml turbid water

Dry yeast concentration (%)	Final turbidity (NTU)					
	40 (min)		50 (min)		60 (min)	
	Alginate	Agar	Alginate	Agar	Alginate	Agar
1	40.08	45.46	36	40.54	34.53	36.31
2	52	58	48.64	55	39.88	47.68
3	61.33	75	55.5	59	58.12	56

Statistical Modeling

Response surface model of the percent turbidity removal outcome. The experimental values for turbidity removal response at the design points and all the three uncoded independent variables for both alginate and agar models are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Experimental design and results for the developed turbidity removal model

Runs	Coded variables		Natural variables				Response (%Turbidity removal)	
	X_1	X_2	g beads/100 water	ml turbid	Settling (min)	Time	Y_1	Y_2
1	+1	-1	3		40		46.7	35.6
2	+1	+1	3		60		55.6	53.7
3	-1	0	1		50		60	55
4	0	-1	2		40		49.9	47.4
5	0	+1	2		60		62.2	59.6
6	0	0	2		50		58.8	59.7
7	-1	+1	1		60		61.6	59.7
8	+1	0	3		50		54.4	52.8
9	-1	-1	1		40		55.5	49.5

Where, Y_1 and Y_2 represent the percent turbidity removal response for alginate and agar beads, respectively. The predicted models for turbidity removal percent in terms of coded variables are expressed in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 representing alginate response (Y_1) and agar response (Y_2) as a function of grams of beads/100 ml turbid water (X_1) and settling time (X_2):

$$Y_1 = 56.08 - 3.40X_1 + 4.55X_2 \quad (1)$$

$$Y_2 = 52.56 - 3.68X_1 + 6.75X_2 \quad (2)$$

The given linear equations in terms of coded variables can be used to make predictions about the percent turbidity removal response for the specified levels of each independent process variables (g beads/100 ml turbid water, and settling time). Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 display the response surface plots designed for the predicted responses for turbidity removal process using alginate and agar beads.

The statistical significance for the developed models for percent turbidity removal response was evaluated by Analysis of variance (Table 5). Table 5 indicates that the p-values of the predicted models were 0.0018 and 0.0185 for alginate and agar, respectively, implying that the two models are significant. Also, the R-squared values for the two developed models equations were 0.88 and 0.74 displayed that the fitting degree of the predicted models were reasonable. So, the two developed mathematical models for both alginate and agar responses can be used to navigate the design space.

Table 5. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for alginate response (Y_1) and agar response (Y_2)

	Sum of squares		Mean squares		F-value		p-value prob>F		R^2	
	Y_1	Y_2	Y_1	Y_2	Y_1	Y_2	Y_1	Y_2	Y_1	Y_2
Model	193.5 8	354.7 8	96.7 9	177.3 9	21.7 7	8.34	0.0018	0.0185	0.88	0.74
Residual	26.68	127.6 9	4.45	21.28						
Total	220.2 6	482.4 6								

Fig. 5. The response surface plot for the alginate beads model

Fig. 6. The response surface plot for the agar beads model

Optimization for the process parameters (g beads/100 ml turbid water and settling time)

Based on the significant predicted mathematical models, the optimum operating parameters for turbidity removal process were identified to maximize the percent turbidity removal. The optimum values were 1.3 g alginate and 1.6 g agar per 100 ml turbid water for 59 min. Maximum turbidity removal percent achieved at these conditions were 62.4 and 59.7%, respectively.

Conclusions

Based on this study, it can be concluded that: 1- Adding 1 g of dry yeast help to improve the ability of alginate and agar beads to remove turbidity from water. 2- Increasing the amount of dry yeast doesn't help to improve the ability of beads to remove turbidity from water. 3- Agar is not a better

choice to remove turbidity from water at these conditions. 4- For high turbidity water, the calcium-alginate system is more effective than for low turbidity water. Moreover, as the initial turbidity decreases the required concentration of alginate and calcium increases.

So, alginate is a high potential to be used as an alternative flocculant for water treatment purposes. This natural flocculant is safer to be used compared to the chemical flocculants and has potential to be commercialized. Thus, it is significant to have additional research on this natural flocculant for the future development of green technology in the water treatment process.

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